

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN VOCABULARY AND WORD

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Annotation: This article discusses the difference between words and vocabulary and their types and analysis.

Key words: Lexicology, linguistic, vocabulary, phraseology.

Today, in order to understand our identity, the need to study our rich history and culture, the unforgettable works of our ancestors, and to know their religious and worldly thinking is increasing. In order to satisfy this necessity, it is natural that it is only through deep and scientific study and comprehensive research of our works. Nowadays, many conditions have been created for us to study and analyze the monuments of the past. One of the important tasks of today is to reveal the rich possibilities of the Uzbek language. Lexicology is a department that studies the composition of the Uzbek language. Lexicology studies the features of the words in the dictionary to express meaning in speech, the activity of use, enrichment, the obsolescence of some words and the phenomenon of meaning migration. Therefore, lexicology is the linguistic basis of the methodology of working on the dictionary. Any speech is made up of grammatically interconnected, content-specific words and word combinations placed in a certain sequence. The richer and more developed a person's vocabulary is, the richer his speech will be; creates a wide opportunity for him to express his opinion in a clear, original and expressive way. Therefore, the richness, variety, mobility of the vocabulary is an important condition for the successful development of speech in the methodology. The modern Uzbek literary language has a huge vocabulary. "The two-volume "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" contains sixty thousand words, and these are only commonly used words." If we add the words given in various terminological dictionaries published in the Uzbek language, synonyms, antonyms, phraseology dictionaries of the Uzbek language and various explanatory dictionaries, the wealth of the vocabulary will increase by thousands. Besides, many words mean many things. For example, from this explanatory dictionary, the use of the main word in more than forty main and phraseology-related meanings is given. One of the important tasks of speech development at school is to improve work on vocabulary, organize it, distinguish and justify its main directions, manage the process of enriching students' vocabulary. Any speech is made up of grammatically interconnected words and phrases that match the content in a certain sequence. The richer and more developed a person's vocabulary is, the richer his speech

will be and will provide ample opportunity to express his thoughts clearly, beautifully and expressively. Dictionary — 1) a set of words in a certain language, its regional or social dialect, found in the works of one or another writer, lexicon; 2) a book in which words (or morphemes, phrases, phrases, etc.) are placed in a certain order (alphabetical, cellular, thematic), descriptive units, their origin, meanings, spelling, pronunciation, stylistic affiliation, translation into other languages. Dictionaries occupy an important place in the spiritual and cultural sphere, they reflect the knowledge gained by the society in a certain period. The dictionary fulfills a number of social tasks: it provides the reader with information about a specific event; introduces him to words in his own and foreign languages; helps to improve and organize the language, its vocabulary. Dictionaries are very ancient (see Lexicography); in the current era, it is of particular importance in collecting information and conveying it to the student. Dictionaries can be divided into 2 main types: encyclopedic and linguistic (philological), dictionaries according to several different characteristics of word description. The encyclopedic dictionary interprets and explains not the words themselves, but the objects and concepts expressed by them. The main purpose of Linguistic Dictionaries is to reveal the meanings and various linguistic features of the word considered as a linguistic unit. Linguistic Dictionaries are divided into several types in terms of content, function and methods of lexicographic description. Dictionaries also perform a number of social tasks: they inform the reader about a specific event; introduces him to words in his native language and in other languages; helps to improve, standardize and organize the language and its vocabulary. Dictionaries appeared in very ancient times. In the previous lessons, information was given about the dictionaries created in the East, in particular, the Turkish language dictionaries. At this point, it should be said that in Europe, especially in Russia, the serious attitude towards dictionaries and the creation of dictionaries began in the 17th century, and the first real explanatory dictionary in Russia also appeared during this period¹. Nowadays, dictionaries are becoming more important in gathering information and conveying it to the reader. There are different types of dictionaries according to their scope, purpose, function and method of description. According to several different features in the description of the word, dictionaries are mainly divided into two types:

- 1) encyclopedic (dictionary) dictionaries;
- 2) linguistic (linguistic or philological) dictionaries.

In turn, each type of dictionary is large, medium, small according to its size; it can be full or short depending on the quantity and processing of the material it covers.

An encyclopedic dictionary and a linguistic dictionary differ in two ways:

- 1) objectively;
- 2) in terms of vocabulary.

Encyclopedic dictionaries provide information about things and events in nature and society, historical events and processes, great people, discoveries in science, states, and cities. Therefore, in dictionaries of this type, the main focus is not on the words in the language, but on the phenomena named by means of these words or phrases.

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